

Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Refactorings for systems implemented in the Elixir functional language

Institution: DCC / ICEx / UFMG

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This “Free and Enlightened Consent” contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand the main refactoring strategies used in code implemented in the Elixir functional language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception about the refactoring strategies in Elixir (use frequency and impact on system quality)

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 20 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucasvegi@dcc.ufmg.br.

If you have questions about the ethical aspects of this research: Contact the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Minas Gerais (COEP-UFMG). Address: Av. Antônio Carlos, 6627. Administrative Unit II – 2nd floor - Room 2005. Pampulha Campus. Belo Horizonte – MG, Brazil. CEP: 31270-901. E-mail: coep@prpq.ufmg.br. Phone: +55 (31) 3409-4592. Opening hours: 09:00 AM to 11:00 AM; 02:00 PM to 04:00 PM (UTC-3).

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Próxima

Página 1 de 4

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Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

Select your country: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

Your city: *

Sua resposta

Voltar

Próxima

Página 2 de 4 [Limpar formulário](#)

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Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

Perceptions on the Relevance and Prevalence of refactorings

Refactoring strategies are code transformations that do not alter a program's behavior. In our research, we aim to catalog and document refactorings for the Elixir programming language. We would like to know your perception regarding these refactorings.

Therefore, based on your experience, answer the questions below.

[Prevalence] How often do you perform this refactoring in your Elixir systems or see this refactoring being carried out in code implemented with this language?
(1 = it is very rare; 5 = it is very common)

[Relevance] How relevant is this refactoring in Elixir systems? (i.e., when answering consider the potential of this refactoring to have a positive impact on maintainability, comprehensibility, and evolution of Elixir code)
(1 = very low impact and relevance; 5 = high impact and relevance)

Notes:

- Each refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link containing code examples;
- You don't have to answer all questions items if you don't want to.

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Extract constant]**.

This refactoring aims to create a constant (i.e., *module attribute*) with a meaningful name for humans and replace occurrences of magic numbers directly in expressions with the extracted constant. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Merging match expressions into a list pattern]**.

This refactoring restructures functions that use the divide-and-conquer pattern, making parallelization easier. To achieve this, it merges a series of match expressions into a single match expression that employs a list pattern. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Add a tag to messages]**.

This refactoring aims to identify groups of messages exchanged between processes that communicate with each other by adding tags. This identification allows for different treatments of received messages. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Simplifying Ecto schema fields validation]**.

This refactoring aims to replace a list of Ecto schema fields created manually, used for validations (i.e., *validate_required/3*), with a call to the *Ecto.schema_/1* function. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Equality guard to pattern matching]**.

This refactoring aims to replace a temporary variable extracted from a *struct* field, that is only used in an equality comparison in a guard, with pattern matching. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Group Case Branches]**.

This refactoring restructures functions that use the divide-and-conquer pattern, making parallelization easier. To achieve this, the branches of a "case" statement in those functions are partitioned, replacing the original "case" statement with separate "case" statements. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Remove redundant last clause in "with"]**.

When the last clause of a "with" statement contains a pattern identical to the predefined value to be returned by this statement in case all checked patterns match, this clause is redundant. This refactoring aims to remove a redundant last clause in "with" and replace the predefined value to be returned by this statement with the expression that was checked in the redundant clause. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Behaviour extraction]**.

This refactoring aims to extract a function that repeats across different modules but serves specific roles in each of them. This function is then abstracted into an Elixir *behaviour*, thus standardizing a contract to be followed by all modules that implement this function. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Pipeline for database transactions]**.

This refactoring aims to convert an anonymous function used to create a pipeline of operations into an *Ecto.Repo.transaction/2* call, transforming it into an *Ecto.Multi* instance (i.e., a data structure used for grouping multiple *Repo* module operations). More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Replace a nested conditional in a "case" statement with guards]**.

This refactoring aims to replace nested conditional statements within a "case" with the use of guards, maintaining the ability to perform more complex pattern matching checks. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Reducing a boolean equality expression]**.

This refactoring aims to replace multiple equality comparisons involving the same variable and logical OR operators with the use of the "in" operator and a list containing all possible valid values for the variable. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Transform to list comprehension]**.

This refactoring aims to transform calls to *Enum.map/2* and *Enum.filter/2* into list comprehensions (i.e., *for* construct), creating a semantically equivalent code. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Simplifying checks by using truthness condition]**.

This refactoring aims to replace an "if...else", that checks an *is_nil/1* call used to return a default value if a given data is indeed null (e.g., *if is_nil(data), do: "default", else: data*), with a short-circuit operator based on truthness conditions (e.g., *data || "default"*). More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[From tuple to struct]**.

This refactoring aims to transform *tuples* into *structs*, which are data structures that allow naming their fields, thus hiding some details of the data representation. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Eliminate single branch]**.

This refactoring aims to simplify the code by eliminating control statements that have only one possible flow. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the prevalence and relevance level of the refactoring **[Introduce import]**.

This refactoring focuses on replacing fully-qualified name calls of functions from other modules (i.e., *Module.function(args)*) with calls that use only the imported functions' names. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

[Voltar](#)

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Página 3 de 4 [Limpar formulário](#)

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Final remarks

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

Yes

No

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

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